

IOT-Enabled smart drip irrigation system agriculture using LORA technology

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Abstract

In this paper, a new method for irrigation systems in agriculture has been reported. This work aims to design and implement a smart irrigation system based on the ESP32 platform and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies for precise and efficient water management. With an increasingly technology-driven world of digital transformation, which is now easily accessible with modern technologies like IoT, where every device is connected and can be controlled through the internet for smart systems, even the agricultural sector is being seen to convert to wiser and more sustainable. With the rapid growth of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, it is now feasible to design smart irrigation systems based on real-time environmental data to deliver maximum water usage with minimal human intervention. In the Sahara areas where there is a lack of communication networks and internet connection, the use of other communication protocols is necessary for data transfer. LoRa technology (SX1278) provides long-range, low-power communication (up to 10-15 km in rural areas) between distributed sensor nodes and a central gateway, making it ideal for large agricultural fields. This project used Arduino software to program the NodeMCU (esp32) board to link the board with the blynk cloud application. The project is used to monitor the temperature, humidity, and soil moisture and do the command for the irrigation system, with master and slave cards by using lora technology as a communication tool to replace communication systems like WiFi or cellular networks in deserted or remote areas. might not offer sufficient coverage or could be too expensive to build. for this purpose, our graduation project aims to develop a smart irrigation system based on the ESP32 microcontroller and LoRa (SX1278) technology, with the long-term objective of helping in the modernization of traditional agriculture and environmental sustainability.

Keywords: Agriculture, Blynk, Cloud, Esp32, Irrigation, Internet of things, Lora technology.

1. Introduction

The conventional irrigation systems suffer from several critical limitations and challenges in modern farming, particularly in desert areas where traditional internet infrastructure is absent. Approximately 70% of global freshwater consumption is attributed to agriculture; The conventional irrigation methods often result in significant water wastage through over-irrigation, evaporation, and poor timing. As climate change intensifies water scarcity and populations grow, the need for an efficient and intelligent irrigation system with new communication techniques is essential. The agricultural industry has previously unheard-of difficulties in maximizing water management while preserving food security due to expanding populations, Precision agriculture now has more options to smart system[1-6] because to the development of Internet of Things (IoT) technology[7-14], The advent of Internet of Things (IoT) technology has revolutionized precision agriculture, enabling farmers to monitor soil conditions, weather patterns, and crop health in real-time. However, most IoT solutions depend heavily on WiFi, cellular networks, or broadband internet connectivity resources that are often unavailable or prohibitively expensive in remote agricultural regions, particularly in developing countries and isolated rural communities. The connectivity by using LoRa (Long Range) technology [15-17] presents a good solution in rural areas where traditional internet infrastructure is absent or unreliable. LoRa can transmit data over distances of 2-15 kilometers; this technology creates an accessible platform for building smart irrigation IoT systems without traditional network infrastructure, Traditional irrigation methods have a number of serious drawbacks that affect environmental sustainability

and agricultural productivity. Usually, these systems follow preset timetables without taking into account current weather patterns, crop needs, or soil conditions. Water waste, nutrient leaching, soil degradation, and less than ideal crop growth are the results of this method, which causes overwatering in some places and underwatering in others. Furthermore, it can be difficult to establish centralized monitoring and control systems in big agricultural fields since they frequently lack sufficient connection infrastructure. For large-scale rural deployments, traditional Wireless sensor networks used in many applications for collecting data about the physical phenomena like WiFi or cellular networks[18-19] might not offer enough coverage or might be too costly. the IoT-based irrigation system utilizing LoRa technology tackles these difficulties by establishing an extensive network of interconnected sensors and actuators that provide precise water management over vast agricultural regions. This system leverages LoRa's long-range, low-power wireless communication capabilities to establish reliable connectivity between distributed field sensors and central control systems.

The solution integrates multiple sensor types including soil moisture sensors, temperature and humidity monitors, and light sensors, to collect real-time environmental data. This information is transmitted via LoRa to centralized gateways and processing systems that analyze the data and automatically adjust irrigation parameters to optimize water delivery. The integration of LoRa technology with IoT-based irrigation systems represents a significant advancement in precision agriculture for several reasons. LoRa's ability to transmit data over distances of up to 15 kilometers in rural environments makes it ideal for large-scale farming operations where traditional wireless technologies fall short. The technology's extremely low power consumption enables sensor nodes to operate for years on single battery charges, reducing maintenance requirements and operational costs.

This paper is organized into several sections to provide a comprehensive understanding of the smart irrigation system development and implementation. after the introduction in Section 2, present a review of related literature on the physical architecture of the smart irrigation system, LoRa communication technology applications in agriculture, and hardware components. Section 3 describes the system overview and design methodology including making automatic irrigation decisions while users have a manual control interface in different network conditions, whether via Wi-Fi and Lora. Section 4 describes the system architecture and design methodology, detailing the hardware components including ESP32 microcontrollers and LoRa modules, sensor integration, and the overall network topology. Section 5 presents the experimental setup and testing procedures used to validate system performance in real-world conditions. We followed a systematic approach starting with a comprehensive theoretical study of the major technologies involved, namely IoT systems, wireless communication protocols, and embedded platforms. Section 6 This was followed by the selection of design, hardware and software building blocks, system implementation and integration, and finally a set of tests to validate its performance, precision, communication range, and power consumption. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper by discussing practical implications for agricultural applications in desert areas and suggesting directions for future research and system enhancements.

2. Literature Review

The physical architecture of the smart irrigation system represents the foundation that assures seamless integration between electronic components and software-based functions. The hardware components were selected and constructed with excellent precision to ensure optimal performance, low power consumption, and intelligent interaction with environmental conditions. This section includes the following parts list of hardware components, Device Definition and Wiring Method (with details to be added later), Mechanical Considerations (including assembly and layout), Electrical Power and Protection, the general Wiring Diagram, and finally the Professional Logical Design. For the selection and integration of hardware components, the literature demonstrates a methodical approach to hardware selection that takes into consideration a number of microcontroller selection variables, including: The majority of solutions employ the use of microcontrollers that can interact with both sensors and LoRa transceivers, such as ESP32 modules or Arduino-based systems. The decision is based on power limitations and processing requirements.

The fundamental problem addressed by this work can be outlined as follows: how do we develop a smart, autonomous, and energy-efficient irrigation system that operates smoothly without

relying on standard power or internet connectivity, yet enable real-time remote monitoring and control? To answer this question, the project set various objectives: creating a hardware framework with robust abilities based on the ESP32 microcontroller, sensors of soil moisture, temperature, and light intensity, and a LoRa transceiver for wireless communication between distant nodes and core ones. Another main objective is to design a simple-to-use monitoring interface through the Blynk application for real-time visualization and control of agricultural conditions. Additionally, the system also optimizes energy consumption by utilizing low-power parts and optimal circuit placement.

In order to accomplish the above, we followed a systematic approach starting with a comprehensive theoretical study of the major technologies involved, namely IoT systems, wireless communication protocols, and embedded platforms. This was followed by design and hardware and software building block selection, system implementation and integration, and finally a set of tests to validate its performance, precision, communication range, and power consumption.

3. System overview

The overview of this design is to enable the system to make automatic irrigation decisions while users a manual control interface through their smartphones and ensuring robust communication in different network conditions, whether via Wi-Fi and LoRa. As shown in figure 1, smart irrigation system, detailing the methods used to meet the project's objectives through a structured analysis of requirements and the integration of hardware and software components. The system design prioritizes reliability and efficiency by utilizing the ESP32 microcontroller, various environmental sensors, and the Blynk platform for remote monitoring. LoRa technology is employed to ensure long-range, low-power communication between master and slave nodes. All design choices were guided by the need for scalability and the humidity and temperature sensor DHT22 measures the humidity and temperature of the air adaptability in real-world agricultural environments

Fig 1 Overview of the IoT-enabled smart irrigation system

The system opens the solenoid valve of the pump to water the plants using a relay. The ESP32 uses lora technology with the mobile application or web dashboard via Blynk cloud. We used the Blynk app to collect irrigation data, manually control the valve, and plot the soil temperature fluctuation graph.

The Arduino IDE was chosen as the working platform for developing the ESP32-WROOM-32D microcontroller. This is one of the most perfect settings for programming the ESP32 platforms due to its high flexibility, ease of use, open-source tools, and the wide help available from the creator and the programmer. In order to set up the Arduino IDE for ESP32, you need to load certain libraries and tools. These assure that the ESP32 unit is fully integrated with the development environment, which makes writing faster and easier.

Using ESP32, Internet of Things, and LoRa, the flowchart intends to illustrate the primary process that is involved in the smart irrigation system. The system is made up of a number of different components and devices that are all connected to one another. These components and devices are

used to monitor and measure factors such as soil moisture and temperature, as well as to manage irrigation automatically. As showing in figure (02) this flowchart displays the main process the smart irrigation system in the master unit, Where the system initialization lora module and sensor data collection (soil moisture, temperature, humidity), the data processing to make the decision by reading the data, LORA receives data from the slave, and transmits it to the master card, and makes decisions and sending the data to the cloud (blynk application) for irrigation control (valve open/close).

Fig 2 the flowchart of master system

In the slave circuit we connected the ESP32 to a solenoid valve, a water flow sensor, a temperature sensor, an air humidity sensor, and a moisture sensor. The ESP32 uses the information from these sensors to decide when to open the solenoid valve by using a lora module. Figure 3 shows the flowchart that shows the logic written into the ESP32

Fig 3 Flowchat of slave system

4. Material used

4.1 ESP-WROOM-32 Microcontroller Unit

Espressif Systems designed the ESP-WROOM-32, an efficient microcontroller chip. It is certainly the most well-known microprocessor module used in IoT (Internet of Things) applications due to it performing effectively, can connect wire-lessly, and uses relatively little power. The module has a Tensilica Xtensa LX6 dual-core CPU and built-in support for both Wi-Fi and Bluetooth It is therefore a wonderful choice for applications that require a large amount of processing power and a wire-less link in a compact, low-cost container.

The ESP-WROOM-32 as shown in figure (04) is designed for embedded systems and Internet of Things (IoT) apps. It has many interfaces and peripherals, Including as PART, SPI, I2C, PWM, ADC, and DAC, give sensors and actuators a lot of different ways to send and receive data. It also has a low-power consumption mode, which makes it good for devices that run on batteries. The microcontroller can also run real-time operating systems (RTOS) like FreeRTOS, which lets it do more than one thing at once for complicated applications.

Fig 04 esp32 card Microcontroller Unit

4.2 LoRa SX1278 Module

The LoRa SX1278 is a wireless transceiver module designed for long-range operation in the 433 MHz band and consumes very little power [20]. The use of LoRa modulation technology enables the achievement of long communication distances with low bandwidth and energy consumption, making it ideal for IoT and sensor networks.

Transmission range requirements, data rate needs, and regional frequency regulations are the basis for selecting appropriate LoRa modules. The LoRa SX1278 is a module that provides long-range wireless communication for low-power purposes in the 433 MHz band. By using LoRa modulation technology, communication distances can be extended and bandwidth can be low, making it perfect for IoT and sensor networks.

Fig 05: LoRa SX1278 Module

4.3 The Capacitive Soil Moisture Sensor

This sensor uses two copper traces implanted on a PCB to measure changes in the soil's dielectric permittivity, which act as capacitor plates. The water content between these plates serves as the dielectric material, and due to water has a higher dielectric property than dry soil or air, a rise in humidity increases the sensor's capacitance [21]. The fluctuation in capacitance is transformed into a quantifiable analog voltage through an integrated oscillator circuit, where moister soil yields a lower

voltage and drier soil results in a greater voltage. The microcontroller's ADC reads the output for real-time soil moisture monitoring. The sensor prevents corrosion and delivers constant readings owing to the absence of direct electrical contact with the soil. capacitive Soil Moisture Sensor v2.0, using with esp32 microcontroller is shown in figure (06) .

Fig 6 The Capacitive Soil Moisture Sensor

4.4 DHT22 Temperature and Humidity Sensor

The DHT22 as shown in figure (07), also known as the AM2302, this device offers a digital output, facilitating its integration with various systems and microcontrollers [22-24], digital temperature and humidity sensor widely utilized in IoT and environmental monitoring applications. It offers high levels of accuracy, stability, and long-term reliability, making it an excellent choice for smart agricultural systems.

The DHT22 features a plastic container that incorporates a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor for identifying temperature. The sensor has four pins, however only three are normally used: VCC, Data, and GND.

The sensor provides data via a single-wire digital interface, enabling for efficient interaction with microcontrollers like the ESP32. It delivers a 40-bit data stream containing 16 bits for humidity, 16 bits for temperature, and 8 bits for the checksum. This sensor offers improved accuracy and a larger measurement range.

Fig 7 DHT22 SENSOR

4.5 Light Dependent Resistor (LDR)

A Light Dependent Resistor (LDR), or photoresistor, it is a passive electrical component, such as the resistance varies depending on the quantity of light falling on its surface. The resistance decreases as the intensity of the light increases, and vice versa. The LDR's simple yet strong behavior makes it excellent for sensing ambient light conditions in a wide range of applications, including intelligent lighting, smart irrigation, and environmental monitoring systems. The sensor serves as a tool to detect and also to know the magnitude. LDR with Arduino UNO to measure light intensity by means of conversion resistance to Lux [25-26].

The LDR is constructed by a semiconductor material as cadmium sulfide (CdS) arranged in a zigzag pattern on an insulating substrate. When photons contact the material, they activate electrons, decreasing its resistance.

Physically, the LDR is a compact and lightweight component with two terminals. Digitally, it acts as a variable resistor, and in microcontroller systems like the ESP32, as shown in figure 08 it's generally utilized in a voltage divider arrangement to create analog voltage values depending on the light intensity.

Fig 8: Light Dependent Resistor (LDR)

4.6 The Water Pump

The 5V water pump as shown in figure (09) is a small and efficient DC motor-driven device frequently utilized in small-scale irrigation of liquid transfer uses[27]. It operates by resulting in a pressure difference to move water through an inlet and exit, making it suitable for automation projects. This pump is particularly valuable in embedded systems for its low voltage needs and straight forward

Fig 9: The 5V water pump

4.7 Relay Module

A relay and as shown in figure (10) is an electromechanical switch that enables a low-power control signal to manage a high-power electrical load, such as a pump or motor. It consists of a coil that, when energized, generates a magnetic field that closes or opens a mechanical contact. In embedded systems [28], relay modules are widely used to interface microcontrollers (like the ESP32) with devices operating at higher voltages or currents than the controller can directly handle. Relays act as switch to control pumps, When the controller receives input from the sensors, it activates or deactivates the relays accordingly [29].in our project, we use a 5V single-channel relay module with an onboard optocoupler to isolate the control circuit from the load circuit, enhancing safety and signal integrity.

Fig 10: Relay Module

5. Experiments and discussion

The main objective of this simulation is to verify the logical behavior of the smart irrigation system in a virtual environment before deploying it on real hardware. Since Proteus does not support the ESP32 microcontroller or the LoRa SX1278 module, equivalent substitutes were used: an Arduino Uno microcontroller in place of the ESP32, and an HC-05 Bluetooth module instead of the LoRa module as shown in figure (11). This emulation allows the core functionalities—such as sensor data acquisition, decision-making logic, and actuator control (e.g., the water pump) to be tested in a controlled and observable environment. by simulating the system using virtual components and serial communication, it becomes possible to observe how the system reacts to changing values of soil moisture and light intensity, while also testing the manual and automatic modes of pump control. The simulation environment thus serves as an essential step in debugging and validating both software and hardware logic before transitioning to the physical deployment phase.

Fig 11: Circuit Schematic in the Simulation Environment

The software design for the 'Smart Irrigation System utilizing ESP32, IoT, and LoRa' project has a significant impact on its seamless integration and responsiveness. the ESP32 microcontroller was chosen as the central processing unit in charge of gathering environmental data (soil moisture, temperature, and light intensity), evaluating it, and performing automated actions based on predetermined logic.

We used the Arduino IDE as the development platform due to its simple to use and suitability with a large range of open-source libraries that enable wireless connectivity, sensor integration, and remote control via user interfaces.

The basic objective of this design is to permit the system to make automatic irrigation choices while providing users with a manual control interface via their cellphones and assuring reliable communication in various network circumstances, whether by Wi-Fi or LoRa.

As shown in figure (12), The Blynk platform plays an important role in enabling real-time communication between the Master ESP32 and the user using cell phones. The Blynk library is used by the Master device to read sensor readings such as temperature, humidity (DHT22), light intensity

(LDR), and soil moisture, which are then wirelessly transmitted to the Blynk cloud. Via Wi-Fi. Blynk provides an excellent platform for creating smart irrigation systems because it offers easy mobile app integration, cloud connectivity, and real-time monitoring capabilities. Here are the key aspects

Fig 12 Blynk IoT dashboard for irrigation system

the sensors value is shown in figure (13), Connected to temperature, humidity, soil moisture, and light sensors and water pump.

Fig 13: Testing Communication Between Modules

As shown in figure (14) and figure (15) the system typically consists of multiple sensor nodes distributed across irrigation zones, each equipped with soil sensors and valve controls. These nodes communicate wirelessly via LoRa to a central gateway that coordinates irrigation decisions based on aggregated sensor data. The global system (master slave) can operate autonomously or sync with cloud services when connectivity becomes available.

This hardware configuration enables reliable, energy-efficient irrigation management in agricultural settings without dependence on continuous internet connectivity. The Blynk platform was configured and linked to the system, enabling real-time monitoring and control. The system demonstrated good performance within a specific range, fulfilling its intended tasks efficiently. Furthermore, the irrigation process can now be triggered either automatically based on sensor readings or manually through the mobile application, offering flexibility and adaptability according to user needs and environmental conditions.

Fig 14 Smart practice irrigation system

Fig 15 (a) Transmitter (Master), (b) Receiver (Slave)

6. Sensor Readings and testing Location

During testing, various environmental sensor readings were collected to verify the accuracy and responsiveness of the system. The moisture Sensor Readings varied from 20% (dry soil) to 85% (wet soil) depending on soil conditions. The irrigation pump was successfully triggered when the moisture dropped below the threshold, the DHT22 temperature and humidity sensor readings the temperature in the range from 22°C to 35°C, with consistent stability. Relative humidity varied between 35% and 80%, reflecting environmental changes accurately. The LDR Light Sensor raw analog value was calibrated and converted to light intensity percentage for better clarity. Light levels ranged from 5% (low light conditions) to 98% (direct sunlight), enabling light-dependent control if needed.

The tests were conducted in an open area near a residential home to minimize obstacles and interference. This location was chosen to simulate realistic environmental conditions and to evaluate the maximum communication range of the LoRa modules. The relatively clear line-of-sight allowed a more accurate assessment of signal degradation over distance.

Table 1: LoRa Communication Range

Distance (m)	RSSI (dBm)	Status
0	-32	Excellent Signal
10	-72	Strong Signal
20	-75	Strong Signal
30	-78	Good Signal
40	-91	Moderate Signal
50	-97	Moderate Signal

60	-102	Weak Signal
70	-100	Weak Signal
80	-105	Unstable Signal
90	-110	Unstable Signal
100	-113	Marginal Signal
120	-115	No Reception

7 Discussion and Conclusion

The smart irrigation system was successfully implemented using ESP32 microcontrollers integrated with LoRa technology for wireless communication in remote agricultural areas. The system was installed across a test field of a few hectares, The LoRa modules operating at 868 MHz depending on region demonstrated excellent penetration through vegetation and reliable performance despite the absence of traditional internet infrastructure. Signal strength remained stable with RSSI values ranging from -85 dBm to -110 dBm across different deployment locations.

The implementation of an IoT-based irrigation system using ESP32 and LoRa technology represents a significant advancement in precision agriculture and water management. This system successfully combines the computational power of ESP32 microcontrollers with the long-range, low-power communication capabilities of LoRa to create an efficient and scalable solution for automated irrigation, this enables deployment across large agricultural fields without the need for extensive infrastructure or frequent battery replacements. The system can operate effectively in remote locations where traditional cellular or Wi-Fi connectivity is limited or unavailable.

This IoT irrigation system using ESP32 and LoRa technology successfully demonstrates how modern embedded systems and wireless communication can transform traditional agricultural practices, offering a practical, efficient, and environmentally responsible solution for precision irrigation management.

Ultimately, this project serves as a valuable practical example of applying modern communication and IoT technologies to optimize agricultural irrigation systems, aligning with sustainable development goals and natural resource preservation. The accomplishments documented in this work lay a solid foundation for future research and industrial applications in the field of smart agriculture.

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